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Sustainable Identities: A Quarrel of Desire and Duty in Wole Soyinka's Play *Death and the King's Horseman*

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Abstract:

Desire and duty seem to be engaged in an eternal quarrel, and Wole Soyinka's play, *Death and the King's Horseman*, powerfully shows this conflict between desires and responsibilities. The term 'sustainability' generally refers to environmental issues. In contrast, this paper applies the concept of sustainability to how an individual or group can maintain its identity and remain strong, consistent, and dynamic, overcoming internal struggles and external challenges. The identity, which can be called sustainable, needs to integrate various elements like personal desires, community commitments, and external influences. Even so, it does not let itself fall apart or lose its direction. This paper examines the conditions that contribute to the development or rupture of such sustainable identities, also seeking a balance. Finally, it explores the repercussions that arise when this equilibrium fails, affecting both the individual and the community at large, as reflected in the play.

Keywords: Sustainable Identities, Quarrel, Reconciliation, Desire, Duty.

Introduction

A very simple yet complex, the word identity means who or what a person or thing is. In general, the word identity refers to the characteristics, experiences, and beliefs that make us

uniquely ourselves. Our identity distinguishes us from the individuals around us and makes us different from others. At the same time, “identity also implies a relationship with a broader collective or social group of some kind” (Buckingham 1). It fosters connections that strengthen our sense of belonging and shared purpose. Identity is significant as it remarkably influences how individuals perceive the world around them and interpret their unique experiences. “It also shapes or is an aspect of how humans make sense of the world and their experiences in it” (McCarthy, Sarah, and Elizabeth 228).

Wole Soyinka's play *Death and the King's Horseman* effectively shows the conflict between personal desires and communal responsibilities. The character Elesin Oba's desires clash with the sacred duties assigned to him through the generations. Thus, under significant internal and external pressures, the extent to which one can sustain one's identity is what this play raises concerns about. It also forces one to consider the delicate balance required to reconcile one's interests with communal responsibility. Needless to say, the play also explores the repercussions that arise when this equilibrium fails, affecting both the individual and the community at large.

Wole Soyinka, the most celebrated Nigerian playwright, novelist and poet, is the first African writer to receive the Nobel Prize in Literature (1986). His various awards and honours, along with the reception of his plays across the globe, reflect Soyinka's literary reputation. An eminent figure in contemporary African Literature, his works are based on the society, culture, tradition and politics of Africa. His lucid writings reveal him as a keen observer of his land, culture and customs with a strong awareness of Yoruba attitudes and aesthetics. The Swedish Academy characterised him as “a writer who in a wide cultural perspective and with poetic overtones fashions the drama of existence” (<https://www.anisfield-wolf.org/winners/wole-soyinka/>).

Death and the King's Horseman is a powerful tragedy by Soyinka. Soyinka himself informs the readers in his 'Author's Note' that the play is based on "events which took place in Oyo, ancient Yoruba city of Nigeria, in 1946" (Soyinka 5). It effectively incorporates Yoruba oral traditions into its story, reflecting the vibrant cultural and spiritual legacy of the Yoruba community. The "threnodic essence" (Soyinka 5) of the play emphasises the tension between personal desire and duty towards the community. The story revolves around Elesin Oba, the King's horseman and his ritual sacrifice, which is significant in Yoruba cosmology and its religious tradition. Following this tradition, Elesin Oba has to fulfil a ritual sacrifice after four weeks of the death of the King so that he can accompany his King in the afterlife. This ritual maintains cosmic balance and helps the King's spirit in its journey to the other world. However, Elesin's interest towards physical pleasures diverts his focus, and he fails to perform the ritual. This failure disturbs the sacred cosmic order of the Yoruba worldview and results in tragedy.

Background and Context

Yorubas believe in the existence of three worlds, "the world of the living, the dead and the unborn" (Soyinka 6). Transitions among these three worlds represent the significant phases of life. Thus, life is an ongoing, continuous process in Yoruba culture. Iyaloja's final words to the Bride, "Now forget the dead, forget even the living. Turn your mind only to the unborn" (76), reinforce this idea. The Yorubas revere the dead as ancestors who serve as guardians and companions to the living. They also believe that the ancestors can come down to the physical world as newborns, so they deeply respect the unborn and hence celebrate *Egungun*.

In Yoruba worldview, *Egungun* is a masquerade which represents the spirits of the ancestors. These spirits come back to the human world for celebration, remembrance and the offering of blessings. This tradition is deeply rooted in Yoruba cosmology, and it highlights the mutual relationship between the living and the dead. The dead are always connected with the living as

they guide, help or punish the living, which entirely depends on their kin's reverence or neglect. The community, while celebrating *Egungun*, performs elaborate rituals and festivities, including drumming, dance, and communal singing. It all creates a festive atmosphere. The role of *Egungun* in this context is significant as a spiritual and cultural cornerstone within Yoruba society.

In the Yoruba belief system, the physical and the spiritual are mutually interconnected. If the community fulfils the spiritual commitments, it prospers and lives peacefully. Elesin's ritual suicide is not merely a personal act; rather, it serves as a communal event that preserves cosmic balance. The rituals in any community "perform certain social needs in the society as they are symbolic expressions of deeper feelings of a social group"(Mekunda 819). When the play begins, it is Elesin Oba's final day. However, he is not alone; the entire community is with him, the praise singers, drummers, and market women. They all participate in upholding their tradition. Their participation shows how the ritual serves to unite them all. "For Yoruba, the emphasis is on community, and community in this context makes no distinction between the dead, the living, and the unborn" (Khanal 94).

The British Empire, aspiring to expand its colonies in the nineteenth century, greatly disturbed the socio-political structure of West Africa. This imperial ambition resulted in the birth of modern Nigeria in 1914. It united various ethnic groups and cultures under a single colonial administration. This administration imposed colonial norms on the daily life of the Nigerians, which marginalised and destabilised traditional African lifestyles. The colonial powers intended to reshape African societal norms and tried to align them with their interests. Thus, "in this colonial worldview, Africa was regarded as the Other, as lagging behind in the level of human development, and often subject to a denigration of its cultures and civilisations"(Ojaruega 262). There was resistance as well as adaptation that marked this

process, as local people struggled to understand colonial governance and its far-reaching impact on their communities.

Simon Pilkings and the Resident are the Colonial authorities in the play. They fail to comprehend the significance of African traditions and hence have a total disregard for the Oyo people's traditions and customs. Labelling it as "barbaric"(Soyinka 31), "nonsense", "mumbo-jumbo" and "pagan" (24), Pilkings and the Resident impose colonial strictures on them. Their ignorance of African beliefs leads them to disrespect what holds sacred value for the locals. During a fancy dress ball dance party, Simon Pilkings and his wife wear the sacred *Egungun* costume, not out of reverence, but in an attempt to entertain and impress the prince and to win the first prize. Unaware of its ritual importance, Simon intervenes in the sacred ritual sacrifice and arrests Elesin Oba. He perceives the ritual sacrifice as nothing more than superstition, failing to recognise its integral role in Yoruba cosmology. He thinks that Western values are inherently superior and refuses to acknowledge the legitimacy of native beliefs. He also forces the community to accept his perception of a tradition that he does not understand.

Quarrel Personified in Elesin Oba:

Elesin Oba, the protagonist in *Death and the King's Horseman*, is a beloved and widely respected figure in his community. The community admires and reveres him. His esteemed status as the King's Horseman is of great cultural significance as it is essential to the well-being of his community. Because of his royal cultural role, his every desire and wish are satisfied by his community as he proudly affirms, "In all my life as Horseman of the king, the juiciest fruit was mine"(18). In the first scene of the play, Elesin, a man of life, passions and vitality who "speaks, dances and sings" with an "infectious enjoyment of life" (9), can be seen entering the market where women own the shops. Elesin's only interest in coming here is to immerse himself in the bustling atmosphere among the women, where he finds true happiness. His words

to the women, suggesting that a man of honour like him deserves to wear elegant and rich clothes, reveal his pride in his social standing and his inclination towards materialistic pleasures. He also boasts that as the king's horseman, he had the privilege of having “the juiciest fruit on every tree” (18) and choosing any woman he desired. Elesin shows confidence and pride when he recounts the tale of the Not-I bird. He tells everyone that this bird flies to individuals, warning them that death is approaching. In response, everyone—humans and animals alike—dismisses the bird, uttering "Not I" and pretending not to hear its message. “Even those we call immortal” (13) have a fear of this bird. However, Elesin boasts that he is unafraid; when the bird visited him, he welcomed it inside so it “flew happily away” and no one will “hear his voice” anymore “in this lifetime.” In self-praise, Elesin says, “You all know what I am”(14). Showing overconfidence, he claims, “My soul is eager. I shall not turn aside” (14).

His desire for a final physical indulgence with the young bride shows that Elesin's love of life is fundamentally linked to his passion for carnal pleasures. His irritation when Iyaloja informs him that the girl “has one step already in her husband's home” (20) reveals that, despite his rhetoric about his community's needs, he cannot restrain his passions and is determined to fulfil his desires, regardless of the consequences. According to tradition, when the king dies, his horseman must follow him to serve him in the next world. Elesin's inherited sacred duty as the King's horseman is to carry out this ritual sacrifice. He must sacrifice himself so the world is not twisted from its proper course. “This is not to say that the death of Elesin Oba is an act of human sacrifice, but the very notion of sacrifice is pivotal in the Yoruba worldview as the propitiatory act by humankind to secure the balance of the cosmos” (Sterling 45).

Acknowledging and emphasising the cultural and spiritual significance of the ritual suicide, the praise singer reminds Elesin to follow his duty. As an ardent follower of the horseman, he observes Elesin's innermost desires. He cautions him that “the hands of women also weaken

the unwary” (10), thus expressing the hopes and apprehensions of his community. Elesin is “a man of enormous vitality” (9) who believes in enjoyments, luxuries and pleasures. At the same time, being the King's horseman, he is aware of his communal and cultural responsibilities. Unfortunately, in his final moments of transition, when a young, beautiful girl attracts his attention, he is caught between his desire for physical pleasure and his public duty. He confesses to the Bride that he is pulled back by “a weight of longing” on his “earth-held limbs”(65). As he is inclined more towards physical pleasures, he falls short in performing the significant ceremonial sacrifice to maintain the balance among the three worlds.

Tradition Sustained in Iyaloja and the Community:

Iyaloja, the "mother of the market" (8), serves as a maternal figure to the women who look up to her. She represents moral authority, wisdom and the resilience of the native values. Knowing Elesin's importance due to his ritual role, she deeply desires to please and ensure his happiness on his final day. Iyaloja requests that the women of the market adorn Elesin in fine clothing. Representing the collective communal conscience, she warns Elesin against pleasures, desires and distractions, as he is “not one who blights the happiness of others for a moment's pleasure”(20). Iyaloja reminds Elesin that cultural responsibilities should precede personal desires. However, afraid of offending Elesin, she remains subservient.

Her deep respect for her tradition and culture makes her surrender her would-be daughter-in-law to Elesin in marriage. She tells the women that, “The claims of one whose foot is on the threshold of their abode surpass even the claims of blood” (21). She asserts the sovereignty of ancestral practices by refusing to support the British colonial authorities and remaining unyielding on Yoruba traditions. Iyaloja reproaches Elesin for failing to fulfil his duty and disrupting the order of Yoruba spiritual practices. She points out that he has left the burden on the women, who must now carry Olunde's body to him. After Elesin's death, Iyaloja criticises

Simon Pilkings for his interference in the lives of others and for inciting chaos within their community. She asserts that both deaths—Elesin's dishonourable suicide and Olunde's ritual suicide—could have been averted had it not been for Pilkings' actions. She encourages the bride to look ahead rather than dwell on the past, emphasising the importance of her future child. Thus, she ensures that indigenous culture remains central despite colonial disruption.

Elesin can see that his people are now adrift, and his weakness has irrevocably altered the established order of their world. Iyaloja mocks Elesin for his cowardice. She also reminds him of her earlier warning that the seed he leaves “attracts no curse” (23). As a result of his actions, he will bear dishonour for the rest of his life. The praise singer recalls the numerous ways he urged Elesin to find a path to the afterlife, recounting his warnings. He also reproaches Elesin, saying he has brought an upheaval in their world's order far beyond their expectations.

Blended Identity and Final Sacrifice of Olunde:

Elesin's eldest son, Olunde, is a sensitive and ambitious young man. He goes to England to pursue his passion for medicine. He also receives support from Simon Pilkings. However, he never gets disconnected from his native traditions despite his exposure to Western values. He views his time in England positively, as it enables him to defend Yoruba culture while also understanding English values. He recognises the significance of an individual sacrificing his life for the greater good. During a discussion with Jane Pilkings about the captain who sacrificed himself at sea, he strongly disagrees with her perspective.

His awareness of the king's death prompts his urgent return to Nigeria, driven by the cultural obligation to honour his father's role within the community. Being the eldest son, he has to bury his father. However, when his father fails to fulfil the transition, Olunde takes his place, ultimately sacrificing his own life to avert disgrace for his family and the Yoruba community. The Praise singer points out and says, “Because he could not bear to let honour fly out of doors,

he stopped it with his life. The son has proved the father Elesin...”(75). Shocked by this role reversal and unable to bear this, Elesin takes his own life. Thus, the colonial intervention turns out to be futile, leading to two deaths. Iyaloja mocks Simon, “The gods demanded only the old expired plantain, but you cut down the sap-laden shoot to feed your pride” (76). Olunde’s sacrifice changes the lives of the people in his community. It shows them the clear path to establish their identities and reject any form of domination, whether internal or external. “His offering of life for the sake of community, which Soyinka considers an affirmation of tradition, is fundamental to Olunde’s integrity and the integrity of his people. Culture is the basis for identity and dignity for a person, but those who betray their culture destroy not just themselves but the whole community” (Khanal 94).

Incidental Colonial Factor

Simon Pilkings, the British district officer for Oyo, Nigeria, is responsible for maintaining control over the local people. His treatment towards the natives reflects cruelty and insensitivity. He is authoritative to those he perceives as beneath him, such as Sergeant Amusa and the houseboy, Joseph. Pilkings also dismisses his wife Jane when she attempts to help him understand the significance of local culture and traditions. Pilkings is inconsistent in his governance, taking action only when he believes it will earn him favour with higher authorities, such as the prince. At a ball, Simon and his wife wear *Egungun* costumes confiscated from Yoruba leaders for mere entertainment. They aim to impress the prince and secure the first prize in a fancy dress competition. This act is seen as deeply disrespectful by Amusa, who, even after converting to Islam, finds it difficult to see the Pilkingses in those costumes.

Pilkings looks at Elesin as a problematic subordinate who is deeply immersed in Yoruba culture and traditions. He tries to prevent Elesin from committing ritualistic suicide as the King’s horseman. For him, this suicide is illegal under his administration. Although he is successful

in stopping Elesin from fulfilling the ritual, he ultimately fails to save his life. Pilkings never realises that his actions have damaged the local culture and traditions.

Sustenance and Rupture of Identities:

Africa is a country of many tribes and clans. Here, it is through their customs and rituals that the Yoruba people connect their identities. "Celebration of traditional ritual in Yoruba culture is the affirmation of the identity of its people"(Khanal 94). This identity is essential and crucial, so society must protect it to ensure safety. Elesin's role in such a culture is to fulfil his duty as the king's horseman, protecting the spiritual wellness and order of the Yoruba people. However, he fails in this responsibility because of his greater interest in worldly pleasures.

When the play opens, it is Elesin's last day among the living. It is a significant moment not only for Elesin but for the entire community, as it coincides with his journey upward to accompany the dead King. On this day, instead of preparing to answer the final call of his friend, Elesin pays more attention to his lust for "a moment's pleasure" (Soyinka 20). He ignores the warnings. The praise singer cautions him and says, "The hands of women also weaken the unwary"(10). Despite numerous warnings about the dangerous consequences of neglecting his duty, Elesin's desire persists. Displaying weakness and selfishness, he marries a young and beautiful girl who has already been engaged to Iyaloja's son. In this way, he disrupts the social order and unsettles the Yoruba community. When he ultimately fails to perform the ritual, his son tries to restore order by stepping in as the king's horseman. In the end, out of guilt and shame, Elesin does take his own life. However, this act does not restore balance or regain his honour. Instead, his failure to reconcile personal desire with communal duty leads to the collapse of his esteemed royal identity and ultimately his physical demise.

Olunde represents a chance at cross-cultural understanding through education. After studying to become a doctor in England, Olunde does not leave his beliefs in Yoruba culture behind.

When he returns from England, he will resume the ritual. Ultimately, it is Olunde who stands out as the only male character to show honour and dutifulness by stepping into his father's role to uphold the spiritual order of his people. Olunde's act is undoubtedly selfless. While reproaching Elesin for his betrayal, the praise singer says that Olunde died to save the "honour of your household and of our race"(75). Thus, Olunde, despite his hybridity, achieves a form of sustainable identity through his ultimate act of communal duty.

However, the Yoruba cosmic order is consequently disrupted. The community now struggles with sustaining its identity amidst internal turmoil and external challenges. Olunde had to assume his father's role in life before taking it in death. With his death, a prevailing sense of abandonment and uncertainty clouds their future as the praise singer observes, "But this young shoot has poured its sap into the parent stalk, and we know this is not the way of life. Our world is tumbling in the void of strangers, Elesin" (75). Their world faces chaos and alienation. A deep sense of disconnection prevails, and the community struggles with a sense of anxiety about its future. This outcome suggests that a failed ritual sacrifice severely disrupted the Yoruba culture. Hence, the formation of a sustainable identity becomes increasingly challenging.

Conclusion

To conclude, Soyinka's play serves as an excellent exploration of sustainable identities. Elesin's pursuit of material and physical pleasures illustrates his strong connection to the living world. Although he professes his commitment to honouring tradition and sacrificing his life, his behaviour suggests his deeper interest in his life than he is willing to acknowledge. He is cautioned repeatedly, but he consistently disregards the warning. Instead of detaching himself from all worldly pleasures, he increasingly entangles himself in the living world and delays the

ritual. This delay leaves scope for colonial intervention, and the district officer, Simon Pilkings, arrests him. Consequently, Elesin is unable to fulfil his responsibilities to both the Yoruba people and their King. His royal identity collapses, resulting in the loss of his honour. Once admired and respected by the entire community, he becomes the target of scorn from the very community. His inability to harmonise personal desires with communal obligations results in the rupture of his identity.

In contrast, both Olunde and Iyaloja successfully reconcile personal interests with public duty and thereby successfully sustain their identity within the community. Olunde stands out as the only male character who represents honour and duty by performing the ritual sacrifice that his father failed to do. Despite his aspiration to study medicine and become a doctor, Olunde sacrifices his life for the collective good- an outlook that sharply contrasts with Jane Pilkings' perspective. In a similar vein, Iyaloja strongly resists colonial interference in the indigenous traditions and holds Simon Pilkings responsible for Olunde's death. She prioritises the well-being of her community over her desires and values Elesin's wishes more than those of her son. Although the young, beautiful Bride is both her son's choice and her preference, she selflessly permits Elesin to claim her for the greater benefit of the community.

However, the world of their community is shattered, beset by fear and uncertainty following the unfulfilled promise of Elesin Oba. The ritual sacrifice, essential to enable them to live lives free from suffering, was significant to their survival and sustenance. At the end, the unborn represent a glimmer of hope in the face of despair, as Iyaloja says to the Bride, "Turn your mind only to the unborn"(76), highlighting the sustaining significance of future generations.

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